
Pre-service Teachers Perception on Adoption of Google Classroom in Mathematics Education in Teacher Training Institutions

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Abstract

The study was on pre-service teachers' perception on the adoption of Google Classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions. Based on the objectives of the study, 2 research questions and a hypothesis were drawn to direct the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The entire population of pre-service teachers in Mathematics Department of Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State Nigeria was used for the study. A 25 -items likert 4-points questionnaire titled "Pre-service Mathematics Teachers Perception towards Adoption of Google classroom (PMTPAGC)" was used to generate data. It had reliability coefficient of 0.91 determined using Cronbach's alpha formula. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions and t-test statistical tool was used to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study indicated a positive perception among pre-service mathematics teachers towards adoption of Google Classroom in Mathematics Education considering the benefits derivable from it. The result was not dependent on programme of study. Based on the result, it was recommended that, Google classroom should be adopted in teaching mathematics in teacher training institutions to enable pre-service teachers enjoy the benefits associated with it.

Keywords: *Mathematics Education, pre-service teachers, Google classroom.*

Introduction

Mathematics teaching and learning in Nigerian education system has always been carried out through the face-to-face mode of learning where the teacher takes the Centre stage in the classroom dictating and controlling the entire process through different methodological approaches. This involved much use of paper and pen on the part of the students and talk and chalk on the part of teachers. Information and communication technology (ICT) has emerged recently and has affected all facets of human endeavor, including education. It has digitalized the education sector in the 21st century such that teaching and learning process is gradually moving away from the conventional face-to-face mode to a new norm of online learning. In this mode of learning, teachers continue their rigorous teaching and learning activities online to ensure that students in their various homes or anywhere continue in their studies. The process of digitalizing mathematics education entails using ICT (information and communication technology) platforms and software to transfer mathematical knowledge across distances. Siemens (2020) refers digitalized education to instructing students of all ages through the use of communication and information technology as well as other digital tools. In view of this, Online learning has grown in popularity in most higher institutions in Nigeria and today, educators are directed to key into the 21st century mode of learning by applying some of the online learning outlets such as the Google classroom.

Google classroom is a platform that allows for free online teaching and learning operated by google for the purpose of furthering education in times of need. Ulum, Fantiro, and Rifa'I (2019) noted that, Google Classroom is a free teaching and learning tool that was created by the search engine giant in 2014 to help students organize, complete, and grade assignments online. Kyslova, Semerikov, and Slovak (2014) posited that, Google Classroom is an interactive educational tool that enables educators to design a rich and informative learning environment by integrating Google Docs, Gmail, Google Drive cloud storage, and other Google applications for teaching and learning. Google Classroom allows students to communicate with their teachers, peers and creates a digital learning environment. It is a free application that integrates e-mails and documents to save into storages. Teachers can upload files, videos, links, announcements and assignments for students to retrieve and view (Phan, 2015, Daramola & Umoru, 2021). Students' and teachers' academic Calendars are adequately considered in a Google Classroom.

A special folder in the associated Google service is generated when a class is created using Google Classroom, allowing students to turn in assignments for teacher grading. Through Gmail, teachers may publish announcements, ask questions, and interact with their students in each classroom. Instructors have the option of adding students straight from the Google Apps directory or by providing them with a code to input in order to join the class (University of Masshacusette.edu, 2016). Google Classroom enhances collaboration, communication between teachers and students, saves time, allows students to organize their files, ask questions, respond to assignments, class work and receive immediate result and feedback. Students can learn remotely or online at their pace and participate actively in the teaching and learning process. Vasu and Shah (2022) claimed that Google Classroom enables teachers to monitor the student's work and performances systematically. Teachers can easily determine the pupils who failed to submit their assignments as assigned actions are linked to tracking systems. Since it is connected to the grading component, teachers may rapidly provide feedback on students' tasks. Google Classroom enables lecturers to distribute lecture materials to the students with ease, plan lectures and meeting periods. It brings fun to teaching and learning which sustains students' interest, motivation and commitment in the entire process. Beaumont (2018) outlined the benefits of Google Classroom, which include

paperless communication, accessibility, and well-organized class administration. It also promotes community communication, organizes folders, shares material, allows assignments to be submitted, and allows real-time viewing of all posted work. Hemrungrote, Jakkaew, and Assawaboonmee (2017) noted that, Google Classroom gives teachers more time to focus on student-centered lessons that let students explore mathematical ideas and encourage conversation among peers. Ghofur (2018) sees Google classroom as one of the learning media based on inquiry learning methods because google classroom can improve students' abilities in discovering, comprehending, researching, analyzing, and developing learning outcomes. Sibuea (2018) opined that Google Classroom supports learning in and outside the classroom, exchange of information and facilitates interaction between students and students or students and teacher.

Perception is regarded as how individual regards, understands and interprets something based on experiences or awareness. Savitra (2017) opined that, perception is a process by which every individual gathers and evaluates their sensory experiences in order to give the world around them meaning. Perception is the process of individual treatment that gives answers, meanings, images or interpretations of what is seen, heard or felt by the senses in the form of attitudes, thoughts and behaviour or referred to as individual behaviour (Orhani, 2021). Abdulsalaam (2022) in a study reported that using Google Classroom has so many benefits among which is fostering communication between students and teachers or among students. Students are also encouraged to learn at anytime and anyplace. The program for pre-service teacher education will benefit greatly from the inclusion of Google Classroom through equipping the would-be teachers with the necessary skills required for 21st-century education. Oyarinde and Komolafe (2020) and Sri Sasmita, Redhana and Suja (2021) in their separate studies reported that the Google classroom platform positively affected students' academic achievement, attitudes and their perception during the pandemic in Nigeria's secondary school. Udosen (2019) as cited in Vasu & Shah (2022) reported that Google Classroom application has proved a valuable platform for distance learners in the National Teachers' Institute Calabar study centre, based on their experience, perceptions and engagement in classroom activities. Iftakhar (2016) in a study on the perception of teachers and students in using Google Classroom at Daffodil International University, revealed that Google Classroom could create functional interactions between teachers and students because it facilitates easy learning of materials. In a survey conducted by Orhani (2021) to find out how students felt about using Google Classroom for math, showed they have positive opinions about it. Annurwanda and Winata (2021) in a study on students' perception towards using Google Classroom for online math learning as seen from students. Reported that the students surveyed expressed their agreement with this tool to learn mathematics, also express that they can interact with their tutors, present tasks, solve questionnaires, see their answers. Senad (2021) reported that, had a favorable opinion of utilizing Google Classroom for maths instruction. Azhar and Iqbal (2018) in their study investigated the teachers' perceptionstowards Google classroom effectiveness in teaching. The resultdid not show any gains of Google classroom towards teaching methodologies. However, it could be used only to upload some assignments forstudents, manage classroom, and to enable teachers to communicate with their students. Zuhrieh, Tareq, Mohammad, and Nahia (2021) reported a positive perception of Google classroom in their study and majority of participants agreed that the Google classroom is easyto create and use.

Studies have shown the benefits of Google classroom in teaching and learning as compared with the regular face-to-face mode of learning. The literatures indicate limited research done in mathematics education within the geographical location of the present study. To fill the

research gap, the present study assessed pre-service teachers' perception towards adoption of Google Classroom in Mathematics education in teacher training institutions.

Purpose of the Study

The study was carried out to assess pre-service teachers' perception towards adoption of Google Classroom in Mathematics education in teacher training institutions. Specifically, the study investigated;

- 1) Pre-service teachers' perception towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions.
- 2) Pre-service teachers' perception towards adoption of Google classroom in Mathematics education based on their program of study.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- 1) What is the perception of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google Classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions?
- 2) What is the difference between the mean responses of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education based on their program of study?

Hypotheses

This hypothesis was formulated for the study

H₀₁: The response means of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education is not dependent on their program of study.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design to assess pre-service teachers' perception towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions. The study was carried out in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State. The population consists of the 65 mathematics pre-service teachers of the institution consisting of 54 Degree and 10 Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). Based on the size of the population, census sampling technique was adopted. A researcher made 15 items likert 4-points questionnaire titled "Pre-service Mathematics Teachers Perception towards Adoption of Google classroom (PMTAGC)" was used to collect data. The instrument had two sections; section A addressed the demographic variables of the respondent while section B dealt with items related to the objectives outline for the study. The response scale ranged from Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) to Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument had its validity ascertained by one expert each from Mathematics Education, Measurement and Evaluation and information and Communication Technology (ICT) Departments of the Institution. Their expert judgments guided the restructuring of the instrument where necessary. The instrument was pilot tested on 30 respondents outside the study group. Their responses gave a reliability coefficient of 0.91 determined using Cronbach's alpha formula which was adjudged adequate for the study. The instrument was administered to the respondents on face-to-face basis through their course leaders and collected on the spot. All the instruments administered were recovered. Using the data generated, the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation based on criterion mean of 2.50. Any item response mean greater than or within 2.50 was

accepted and any below that was rejected. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool.

Result Research Question 1: What is the perception of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google Classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions?

Table 1: Summary of Pre-service teachers' responses on adoption of Google Classroom in Mathematics education

S/N	Item	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Google classroom is a comfortable online learning environment.	65	3.05	0.71	Accept
2	Google classroom allows me to learn from the comfort of my home or anywhere.	65	3.12	0.69	Accept
3	Google classroom allows me to engage in collaborative learning with my colleagues.	65	3.00	0.74	Accept
4	Google classroom enables me access my course materials.	65	3.21	0.58	Accept
5	Google classroom enables me to receive and respond to my mathematics assignments.	65	3.01	0.69	Accept
6	Google classroom makes it possible for me to participate in mathematics class activities	65	3.03	0.70	Accept
7	I can have unlimited interaction with my lecturers through Google classroom.	65	3.11	0.63	Accept
8	Google classroom enables me seek solution to mathematical problems from my lecturers.	65	2.98	0.81	Accept
9	Google classroom is easy to access.	65	3.13	0.69	Accept
10	The direct comments on my assignment from my lecturer motivates me to improve on my problem-solving abilities.	65	2.95	0.82	Accept
11	Google classroom brings virtual opportunity for mathematics course materials.	65	3.25	0.65	Accept
12	Using Google classroom to learn mathematics leads to development of creative skills.	65	3.00	0.72	Accept
13	Google classroom enables one to share course materials with colleagues.	65	3.07	0.67	Accept
14	I can monitor my academic progress through Google classroom.	65	3.04	0.70	Accept
15	Google classroom makes learning of mathematics easy.	65	3.21	0.62	Accept
16	Learning mathematics with Google classroom is expensive.	65	3.45	0.59	Accept
18	Power supply hinders my use of Google classroom.	65	3.25	0.62	Accept
19	I'm always distracted when using Google classroom.	65	2.85	0.80	Accept
20	The use of Google classroom in mathematics learning enables me concentrate on my work.	65	3.02	0.73	Accept
21	Learning with Google classroom saves time	65	3.41	0.55	Accept
22	The use of Google classroom in mathematics learning saves transportation cost.	65	3.35	0.59	Accept

23	Learning mathematics with Google classroom is better than face-to-face learning.	65	2.87	0.91	Accept
24	Learning mathematics with Google classroom enhances critical thinking skills.	65	2.93	0.83	Accept
25	Learning mathematics with Google classroom has helped me develop digital skills.	65	3.25	0.63	Accept
	Grand Mean		2.98	0.67	

The summary of pre-service mathematics teachers' responses in table 1 shows that all the items were accepted as they had response means greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. Also, grand mean of 2.98 with standard deviation of 0.67 stands above the grand mean. The result implies a positive perception among the pre-service mathematics teachers towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education.

Research Question 2: What is the difference between the mean responses of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education based on their program of study?

Table 2: Summary of mean responses between Degree and NCE pre-service teachers

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean diff	df	t-cal	t _{0.05}	Decision
Deg.	54	2.96	0.69	0.03	62	0.136	1.999	NS
NCE	10	2.93	0.65					

Summary of mean responses between Degree and NCE pre-service teachers in table 2 shows that, Degree pre-service mathematics teachers had response mean of 2.96 and standard deviation of 0.69 while their NCE counterparts had response mean of 2.93 and standard deviation of 0.65. These resulted to a mean difference of 0.03 in favour of the Degree pre-service teachers.

H₀₁: The response means of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education is not dependent on their program of study.

Table 2 shows that, the calculated value of 0.136 is less than the table value of 1.999 at 0.05 level of significance of degree of freedom 62. Based on the result, the hypothesis is upheld which implies that, the response means of pre-service teachers towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education is not dependent on their program of study.

Discussion

The result of the study revealed that pre-service mathematics teachers are comfortable with Google classroom learning environment as it allows them learn from any distance, collaborate with colleagues, access course materials, receive and respond to assignment in time, participate in learning activities, interact with lecturers, develop problem solving skill, become creative, brings virtual access to learning among others. They also expressed that, learning mathematics with Google classroom is expensive, prone to distractions and depends on power supply. The items were all accepted as they had response means greater than the instrument criterion mean. Also, the grand mean was above the criterion mean which was an indication that, irrespective of the challenges associated with Google classroom, mathematics pre-service teachers had positive perception towards it. The result is in line with the report of Kassim (2021) which revealed that Google classroom is highly useful to students as it helped

them be more productive, allowed them to access materials conveniently and submit assignments quickly, and enabled them to interact with the lecturer and other students. Also, Senad (2021) who earlier reported positive perception among students on using Google Classroom in mathematics.

The study also revealed that degree pre-service teachers had a slight difference in response mean with their Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) counterparts in favour of Degree pre-service teachers. Further statistical analysis did not show any significant difference between their response means. This implies that both groups did not differ in perceptions towards adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions. The result is in line with the earlier finding of Zuhrieh, Tareq, Mohammad, and Nahia (2021) which revealed a positive perception on Google classroom in their study and further noted that majority of participants assured that the Google classroom is easy to create and use.

Conclusion

The result of the study has revealed that pre-service mathematics teachers irrespective of their program of study, have positive perception towards the adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education in teacher training institutions. This result is highly encouraging as adoption of Google classroom in mathematics education is beneficial and will prepare pre-service teachers for the task ahead.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made,

- 1) Google classroom should be adopted in teaching mathematics in teacher training institutions to enable pre-service teachers enjoy the benefits associated with it.
- 2) Mathematics educators should be information and communication technology competent to be able to adopt Google classroom in teaching.
- 3) Conferences, workshops and seminars should be organized by Government and school managers to train educators on adoption of Google classroom in teaching and learning.

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